

MODELING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE TEACHERS THROUGH COMPUTER TRAINING

Uktamov Madadjon Uktam ugli

Shahrisabz State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8364051>

***Abstract.** Criteria for evaluating the levels of development of the components of professional competence by teaching informatics to future teachers of pedagogy and psychology have been developed, at the same time, a methodical model of informatics education using computer technology tools has been developed and put into practice. Software products for the subject of "Informatics" aimed at developing the components of professional competence of young teachers with the help of computer technologies were developed and put into practice.*

***Keywords:** method, competence, component, program, monograph.*

We built a conceptual model to verify the conditions described in the hypothesis of this research and determined as a result of theoretical analysis, the conditions for the formation of the future technology teacher's readiness to use computer technologies in the educational process. In the construction of the model we are interested in, we referred to the methods developed in the modern pedagogical theory of modeling the didactic process in a higher education institution and to the models created by modern researchers for the formation of various aspects of preparation for professional pedagogical activities.

The information-semantic model of learning is described in detail in the works of L. T. Turbovich. The main idea of such modeling is that learning information is presented as a sequence of messages (concepts, judgments, norms) and this sequence should be chosen in such a way that learning is most effective. As stated in the monograph "Informative-semantic model of education", "any method of selecting educational information approaches the optimum only if it takes into account the level of knowledge, skills and qualifications of consumers of educational information, their system of ideas".

In accordance with the purpose presented by us (see the professionogram), the process of forming the readiness to use computer technologies in the pedagogical process in the system of the general professional training of the future technology teacher consists of three interacting components:

- formation of the orientation of the future informatics teacher to the use of computer technologies in his professional activity;
- formation of special knowledge and skills in the field of information and computer technologies;
- formation of methodical knowledge and skills in the use of computers.

These data constitute the target block of our model, on the basis of which we selected the content of the training of technology teachers for the teaching process using computers as a universal modern didactic tool to support the educational process of students of educational institutions .

We had to identify the subjects, as a result of studying them, it is possible to form the future teacher's direction, special and methodical training in the field of using computer technologies. We began this search by analyzing the content of the basic teacher training defined by the State Education Standard, as a result of which we found the academic subjects that we wanted to use to form the readiness to use computer technologies. The courses "Informatics", "Information technologies" and "Technical and audiovisual educational tools" at the Faculty of Pedagogy are such subjects.

If the methodological model is considered as a continuous system from the goal to the result, it requires the consistent implementation of the algorithmic sequence implemented in the training of the future specialist. The following organizational-pedagogical, organizational-functional, pedagogical-psychological, thematic-didactic conditions are provided for the full functioning of the system of training future pedagogy and psychology education teachers for professional activities and their competence in using computer technologies. we believe it can be effective. These include the following. Development of training programs for the training of future pedagogy and psychology education teachers, taking into account the trends in the development of modern information and communication technologies;

- to create a new information and educational environment for training specialists who have the ability to effectively use modern information and communication technologies in the future;

- to give students the opportunity to create a personal electronic environment for individualization of professional training as a future pedagogue; Electronic environment means information systems (Hemis, Moodle), e-mail, chat, chat-forum, ISQ, IP-telephony, blogs, video blog, live journals, Wikipedia, interactive media technology, online video conference systems.

- to provide a high-quality material and technical base of preparation for professional activity;

- extensive use of modern information and computer technologies in the educational process;

- establishing strong relations with employers;

- organizing and conducting pedagogical and production practices focused on the use of modern pedagogical and information technologies.

Development of methodological approaches and didactic principles in the process of formation of professional skills of future teachers of pedagogy and psychology;

- theoretical and practical training of the teacher in information and computer technologies for the formation and development of digital competence;

- organization of a digital educational environment;

- improvement of the curriculum and programs based on the credit-module system of education.

- development and constant updating of educational materials and information resources for electronic education;

- individualization of education, creating conditions for determining the personal educational trajectory of the future engineer-pedagogue

- establishing mutual cooperation relations with industry and employers;

- development of the motivation system for in-depth study of the field of science;

- to determine the competency groups included in the programming professional competencies of future specialists and to carry out continuous monitoring;

- selection of the content of professional training of future pedagogic and psychological education teachers;

- development and constant updating of educational materials and information resources for quality training of future pedagogy and psychology education teachers;

- use appropriate forms, methods, tools, methodical approaches and teaching technologies to form programming competence of future pedagogy and psychology education teachers;

- involving future teachers in self-management, self-education and self-development;

- introduction of effective forms and methods of education into the educational process, taking into account modern advanced forms of teaching, new pedagogical and information technologies, optimization of the educational, psychological and physical load of students

- formation of target criteria for the formation of highly educated personnel, optimization of the programs implemented in higher education institutions in the areas of specialization and specialized areas and fields, taking into account the needs and requirements of economic sectors and the prospects of comprehensive development of the region. Thus, in accordance with the selected approaches and principles, on the basis of the model of professional competence formation, we understand a model that includes purposeful, methodological, substantive, pedagogic and psychological and evaluation components.

Pedagogical conditions can be divided into three large groups: provision of organizational-pedagogical conditions mainly involves the development and development of science programs, curricula, requirements, and content development of educational and methodological support; development of various methods for pedagogical and psychological conditions and their application to the educational process, development of psychological games, development of developments and technologies that serve the formation of emotional and mental actions of students; didactic conditions include the development of educational manuals and textbooks, electronic methodical manuals, electronic versions of didactic games for students of educational institutions up to the educational institution.

REFERENCES

1. Abduqodirov A.A. N.D.Mamatov va boshqalar. Axborot texnologiyalari. – T.: O‘qituvchi, 2002. – 133 b.
2. U.Yuldashev, R.R. Boqiyev, F.M.Zokirova “ИНФОРМАТИКА” Toshkent. 2002 yil.
3. Современные языки программирования: учебное пособие / Ф. М. Закирова. Л. М. Набиулина: Мин-во высшего и среднего спец. образования РУз, Национальное общество философов Узбекистана. 2012. -192 с
4. Ходжаев Б.Х. Умумтаълим мактаби ўқувчиларида тарихий тафаккурни модернизациялашган дидактик таъминот воситасида ривожлантириш. Пед. фан. док. ... дис. – Тошкент. 2016.
5. Усаров Ж.Э. Компетенциявий ёндашувга асосланган давлат таълим стандартларини амалиётга жорий этиш: муаммо ва ечимлар // Физика, математика ва информатика. – Тошкент, 2016. - № 6. – Б. 40-48.
6. Aripov M., Begalov B., Begimqulov U., Mamarajabov M. Axborot texnologiyalari. O‘quv qo‘llanma. T. Noshir. 2009, 368 b.
7. Смирнов Е.Н. О воспитании информационной культуры студентов вуза. -Л.: ЛГПИ,1990.-54 с.